

MULTIDIMENSIONAL POVERTY AND COPING STRATEGIES AMONG FARMING HOUSEHOLDS IN NORTHWESTERN NIGERIA

IBRAHIM H.I. and IBRAHIM H.Y.

*Department of Agricultural Economics, Faculty of Agriculture
Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State Nigeria*

Corresponding Author [E:Mail:Hassanisahqibrahim@gmail.com](mailto:Hassanisahqibrahim@gmail.com) Phone Number:08036980580

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.0202505030>. 20

ABSTRACT

*Multidimensional poverty continues to pose a major development challenge in Nigeria, despite the nation's abundant economic potential and numerous poverty alleviation initiatives. This study examines the determinants and dimensions of multidimensional poverty among farming households in North-western Nigeria by analysing its intensity, drivers, and coping strategies. Using data collected from 270 farming households, the study employed descriptive statistics and the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) developed by Alkire and Foster (2011). The results revealed that 58% of households are multidimensionally poor, with an average deprivation intensity of 53%. The computed MPI value of 0.3074 underscores the severity of poverty in the region. Major deprivations were observed in education, sanitation, and asset ownership. Weak governance, low educational attainment, poor access to basic amenities, insecurity, and environmental degradation emerged as significant drivers of multidimensional poverty. Coping mechanisms adopted by farming households included farm diversification, engagement in off-farm activities, skill acquisition, and informal borrowing. The findings highlight that multidimensional poverty among farming households in North-western Nigeria is both widespread and deep, driven by structural and institutional weaknesses. Addressing it requires integrated policy approaches that strengthen governance, enhance access to quality education and healthcare, improve rural infrastructure, and expand livelihood opportunities. Finally, poverty alleviation policies should move beyond income-based measures to address the overlapping deprivations limiting human capability and productivity. Empowering farming households through inclusive, multi-sectorial, and participatory development interventions is essential for achieving sustainable rural transformation and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030. **Keywords:** Determinants, Farming Households Multidimensional Poverty, Northern Nigeria, Poverty, Sustainable Development*

INTRODUCTION

Multidimensional poverty is still a significant challenge in Northern Nigeria, hindering the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Despite Nigeria's economic growth, poverty persists, and its effects on human well-being and sustainable development are profound. The absence or inadequate comprehensive data on multidimensional poverty and its relationship with SDG achievement in Northern Nigeria

creates a knowledge gap, making it difficult to design effective poverty reduction strategies.

Northern Nigeria is grappling with severe and persistent multidimensional poverty, with a rate exceeding 76%, significantly higher than the national average of 63% (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2021). Given the Nigeria's numerous economic potentials, households' deprivations in dimensions such as health, education, and living standards

ought to be minimal. A conspicuous distribution of multidimensional poverty in all the geopolitical regions of the country is evident. However, the northern states and their rural areas are the worst hit. Many programmes have been implemented to address poverty, but poverty is still widespread. It is worrisome to know that 36.8 % of children in Nigeria are stunted and the child mortality rate stands at 132 deaths per 1000 live births, in addition only 39 per cent of rural households have access to electricity, 69 per cent of Nigerian households use solid fuel; 74 per cent of urban and 58 per cent of rural households have access to potable water; the net school attendance ratio (NAR) is 61 per cent at the primary level and 49 per cent at the secondary level; and only 56 per cent of Nigerian households have access to an improved sanitation facility (National Population Commission NPC & ICF, 2019). These facts indicate that a substantial percentage of Nigerians live in different dimensions of poverty. This poverty is characterized by overlapping deprivations in education, health, and living standards, making the region one of the poorest in the country. Despite various poverty reduction initiatives, these high rates present a formidable obstacle to meeting up with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 1 (No Poverty), 3 (Good Health and Well-being), and 4 (Quality Education) (Leal Filho et al., 2022). The situation is worsened by the region's specific socio-economic conditions, such as low school enrolment, poor health outcomes, and inadequate infrastructure (NBS, 2021). These issues perpetuate a cycle of poverty that is challenging to break without targeted interventions. The prevalence of multidimensional poverty not only prevents regional development but also undermines national efforts to meet the SDGs 5 years from now.

To address these challenges, a

comprehensive understanding and nuanced approach to poverty assessment and intervention is necessary. Previous studies on multidimensional poverty in Northern Nigeria have utilized various tools and methodologies such as the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI). This tool, developed by the Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), assesses poverty by looking at multiple deprivations across different dimensions, such as education, health, and living standards.

The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) offers a valuable framework for understanding and addressing the multiple dimensions of poverty in Northern Nigeria. By providing a detailed analysis of contributing factors, the MPI can address some of the limitations of previous tools, such as by offering more context-specific insights and a more granular view of deprivations (NBS, 2021; Leal Filho et al., 2022). Hence, it is against this background that this study seeks to estimate the level of multidimensional poverty status among farming households in Northern Nigeria. The broad objective of the study is to estimate the determinants of multidimensional poverty status among farming households in the study area. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents;
 - ii. determine the multidimensional poverty status of the respondents;
 - iii. determine the dimensional share to the various components of multidimensional poverty status;
 - iv. identify the drivers of multidimensional poverty in the area; and
- identify coping strategies against multidimensional poverty in the area

The findings would be beneficial to

polycymakers, development institutions, and organizations to initiate programmes that will curtail poverty. It will provide policy insights and directions that will guide development agencies, organizations, institutions, and the government on the design and implementation of poverty reduction strategies for farming communities. Also, the findings of the research can be used as references for further research on multidimensional poverty.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in northern Nigeria. Northern Nigeria roughly spans the coordinates: **Latitude:** 10° to 15° N and **Longitude:** 8° to 14° E. Northern Nigeria is a diverse and expansive region of the country, popular for its rich cultural heritage, varied landscapes, and significant socio-economic dynamics. It is the largest and most populous region in Nigeria, characterized by a mix of urban and rural areas, with a wide range of ethnic groups, languages, and traditions. The Northwest zone of the country was used for the study. This zone includes states such as Kano, Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara. Three states (3) namely Kano, Kaduna, and Katsina were purposively selected due to their relatively low level of

insecurity. Ten percent (10 %) of the Local Government Areas in each of the States were randomly selected as the study areas. This resulted into four, three and two LGAs from Kano, Katsina and Kaduna states respectively. A sample of 30 farming households was selected in each LGA because it is appropriate for a standard normal deviation and statistically ideal to get a meaningful result from a study (Mensah et al., 2020). Therefore a total of 270 respondents from the three States were used as respondents for the study. Data was collected using a questionnaire designed with the Kobocollect Open Data Kit (ODK) tool. 4kn 23kd 34kt Descriptive statistics was used to achieve the objectives I, iv and v of the study. The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), as adopted from IFAD (2014), was used to achieve objectives ii and iii of the study.

The MPI is an international measure of acute poverty which identifies the level of deprivations at the household level and it also shows the number of multidimensionally poor people. Computation of MPI begins with scoring of each of the indicators so that zero is assigned when not deprived and 1 when deprived. The weighted scores of these indicators was computed as:

$$C_i = w_1I_1 + w_2I_2 + \dots + w_n I_n \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where $I_i = 1$ if the person is deprived in indicator i and $I_i = 0$ otherwise, and w_i is the weight attached to indicator i with

$E^{w_i} = 1/A$ poverty cut-off point (k) was defined in order to identify those who are multidimensionally poor. Applying the Alkire and Foster (2011) method, the k will be set at 0.33 in this study. According to Alkire and Santos (2011), the MPI integrates two key components of household information: First, is the prevalence of poverty or the proportion of people (within sampled farming households) who experienced multiple deprivations, also known as multidimensional headcount ratio (H). The equation is written as:

$$H = \frac{q}{n} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: q is the number of households who are multidimensionally poor and n is the total sample size of the households.

The second piece is the intensity of their deprivation—the average proportion of (weighted) deprivations they experience

$$A = \frac{\sum C_i}{nq} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where C_i is the weighted deprivation score of individual household i , and q is the number of households who are multidimensionally poor. Following Alkire et al. (2011) and Aboaba et

$$MPI = H \times A \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

A household is identified as non-poor if the weighted indicator is < 0.33 , multidimensional poor if the weighted indicator of poverty ranges from > 0.33 to < 0.50 , but severely poor if MPI is \geq to 0.50 of (declining physical labour capacity with increasing age, slower uptake of novel but potentially labour-saving technologies).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The finding that 90% of respondents are male concurs with the majority of studies in rural Nigeria. In most cases, male heads of households are the primary respondents for labour supply, especially family labour and decision-making. This is particularly true for smallholder farmers who rely on family labour supply and intergenerational transfer of farming knowledge, but also showing a mean household size of 10 persons is considerably larger than many rural surveys. For instance, studies in Oyo State reported means closer to 8 persons per household, and another study in Oyo State reported a mean household size of 9 persons. These observations can be interpreted in multiple ways: possibly extended family living arrangements, high dependence on grandparents, high fertility. This has some consequences for programming and policy.

Programme for rural extension, have a mean age of 45 years, with the bulk of respondents in the 30–59 years brackets. Farming experience is substantial, with a mean of 22 years, and about 42% of respondents having 21–30 years of experience. These results align with many recent Nigerian studies in which smallholder farmers tend to be middle-aged and deeply experienced. For example, Mailumo et al. (2024) in a study of sorghum farmers in Northwest Nigeria found a mean

age of ~47 years. This reflects both the low involvement of youth and the retention of farming by experienced practitioners. Such an age profile suggests both advantages (knowledge, know-how) and constraints

household dynamics, and labour With only 22% having access to credit and availability. On the positive side, larger 78% without, this result underscores a households may have more labour persistent constraint in smallholder (especially family labour), but may also agriculture. Many studies report similarly have greater dependency burdens (children, low formal credit access among rural elderly), which may strain household farmers. However, some studies find higher resources. Education (formal schooling) aggregate access when informal credit or among respondents shows that 40% have group/cooperative credit is included. For secondary education, 34% have no formal example, the rice farmers in Abuja had education, and primary makes up the rest ~67% access when including all loan (~26%). Education is well known to sources. The mean farm size in your sample correlate with adoption of innovation, input is 2.79 ha. This qualifies the respondents as use, credit-access, and risk management. smallholder farmers (often classification is Thus, the moderate level of secondary ≤ 5 ha). The somewhat larger mean might education in this sample is a favourable indicate agro-ecological or land tenure sign, though the substantial proportion conditions that allow for slightly larger without formal schooling suggests literacy, holdings, or less land fragmentation, or numeracy, and extension delivery perhaps inclusion of fallow or marginal challenges remain. lands in the size measure.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Farming households in north western Nigeria

S/N	Socio-economic variables	Frequency	Percentages
1	Age group		
	20-29 30-39 40-49	25	09
	50-59	76	28
	60-69	84	31
		54	20
		31	12
	Mean = 45		
2	Gender		
	Female	27	10
	Male	243	90
3	Marital status		
	Marri ed	252	94
	Sing le	18	06
4	Membership of Association		
	Yes	39	15
	No	231	85
5	Household size		
	0-6 7-13 14-20 2	102	38
	1-27 Mean =10	104	39
		52	19
		12	04

6	Level of Education		
	No Formal Education	92	34
	Primary	70	26
	Secondary	108	40
7	Years of Experience		
	1-10 11-20 21-30	70	26
	Mean = 22	86	32
	Access to credit	11	42
		4	
8			
	Yes No	59	22
	Farm size	211	78
9	0-2.99 3-		
	5.99		
	6-8.99	103	38
	Mean = 2.79	112	42
	TOTAL	55	20
		270	100

Estimation of Multidimensional Poverty Index The numbers of deprived households in each dimension are presented in Table 2. Majority of the households that is 203 out of 270 (75%) households are deprived in assets. Furthermore, the deprived households in sanitation and years of schooling had quite high that is 69.57% and 41.17% respectively. There are no households deprived in child mortality from the sampled households in this study. Considering the dimensions, many households are deprived in standard of living while only 6 households deprived in health dimension through nutrition.

Table 2: Number of deprived households in each indicator

Dimensions of MPI		Number of deprived households & (%)	Weight
Health	Nutrition	6 (2.3%)	
	Child mortality	0	1/6
Education	Years of schooling	111 (41.17%)	1/6
	School attendance	5 (1.7%)	1/6
	Cooking fuel	19 (7.25%)	1/6
Living Standard	Sanitation	187 (69.57%)	1/18
	Drinking water	16 (5.8%)	1/18
	Electricity	71 (26.47%)	1/18
	Housing	87 (32.35%)	1/18
	Assets	203 (75%)	1/18
			1/18

The multidimensional poverty indices are presented in Table 3. The headcount ratio of 0.58 means that 58% of the households in the sample are multidimensionally poor that is, they experience deprivations in one-third or more of the weighted indicators used in the analysis (such as health, education, and living standards). A high H indicates widespread poverty: most households are deprived in multiple non-monetary dimensions of wellbeing. In other words, more than half of the sample population suffers simultaneous disadvantages that go beyond income, including poor education, poor access to

healthcare, and inadequate living standards. In the context of Northern Nigeria, this aligns with national statistics. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and UNDP (2022) report that multidimensional poverty is highly concentrated in the northern states, where over 65% of residents are poor compared to below 30% in most southern states.

The Intensity of Poverty (A) is 0.53 implying that, on average, each poor household is deprived in 53% of the total number of indicators. In simpler terms, the poor are not just many they are deeply poor. They do not possess enough of the basic

capabilities and services considered incidence and intensity of poverty. An MPI essential for a decent life. A value of A = 0.53 suggests that interventions must not only reduce the number of poor households reference, Nigeria's national MPI in 2022 (0.47) but must also reduce the depth of deprivation. Zamfara and Jigawa recorded MPI values above 0.50 (NBS & UNDP, 2022). The MPI of 0.3074 thus indicates that the adaptation and health care multidimensional poverty through the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), the matching the poverty profile of the poor product of H and A summarizes both the northern states.

Table 3: Multidimensional poverty indices of farming households

Variables	Values
Head Count Ratio (H ₀)	0.58
Poverty Intensity (A ₀)	0.53
Multidimensional Poverty Index (M ₀)	MPI = H*A = 0.58*0.53
MPI poor	58.0%
MPI Non Poor	42.0%

Policy Discussion and Implications The combination of a high H (0.58) and moderate-to-high A (0.53) suggests that poverty in the study area is both widespread and intense many households are poor, and they experience multiple deprivations simultaneously. This pattern calls for integrated poverty-reduction strategies rather than isolated interventions. Key policy directions include:

- i. Education and skill development: Tackling the high deprivation in schooling and literacy can have multiplier effects on other poverty dimensions.
- ii. Improved access to healthcare and nutrition programs: Reduces health-related deprivations and improves productivity.
- iii. Infrastructure and social amenities: Investment in electricity, water, and sanitation would directly reduce living

standard deprivations. iv. Gender and youth targeting: Women and youth often experience higher deprivations; targeted empowerment programs can reduce intra-household poverty.

Multidimensional Poverty Figures for selected States are presented in Table 4. Katsina (MPI = 0.536) records the highest multidimensional poverty, showing widespread and deep deprivation. Kano (0.235) follows with a moderate MPI, reflecting a balance between urban prosperity and rural poverty. Kaduna (0.185) ranks lowest, benefiting from better infrastructure, education, and social services. The pattern corresponds with NBS (2022) findings that rural-dominated northern-western states like Katsina exhibit higher multidimensional poverty than more urbanized ones like Kaduna.

Table 4 Multidimensional Poverty Figures for selected States North-western Nigeria

State	Headcount Poverty		MPI (H × A)	MPI Poor (%) MPI Non-poor (%)	
	Ratio(H)	Intensity (A)			
Katsina	0.66	0.54	0.47	66.0	34.0
Kano	0.50	0.42	0.356	50.0	50.0
Kaduna	0.44		0.235	44.0	56.0

In terms of Headcount Ratio (H), Katsina's 0.66 suggests two-thirds of households are multidimensionally poor, a result of weak access to education, limited non-farm income sources, and poor living conditions. Kano's 0.50 indicates that half of its households experience deprivation, though urban centres like Kano metropolis improve the average. Kaduna's 0.44 implies a smaller share of poor households, showing relatively successful social interventions and stronger urban economies. The Poverty Intensity (A) or Depth of Deprivation for Katsina is 0.54, implying that the poor experience deprivation in over half of all

Kaduna (0.42) has the lowest intensity, the poor there are less deeply deprived.

A Comparative socioeconomic overview as presented in Table 5 shows that Katsina is most deprived overall as rural education and

sanitation remain critical issues. Katsina experiences an urban-rural divide, economic vibrancy in cities contrasts with rural deprivation. Kaduna has a comparative advantage in infrastructure and governance quality, explaining its lower MPI. The figures suggest that within North-western Nigeria, Katsina remains the poorest, Kano is moderately deprived, and Kaduna is relatively well-off. This pattern reflects the interplay of geography, governance, and economic structure, reinforcing the need for targeted, state-specific poverty alleviation policies.

weighted indicators (health, education, and living standards). Kano (0.47) shows milder intensity, as most poor households lack 2–3 dimensions rather than many.

Table 5 Comparative socioeconomic overview of Selected States in North-western Nigeria

Dimension	Katsina	Kano	Kaduna
Education	Very low literacy; gender gap high	Moderate literacy, especially in cities	Higher literacy and school completion
Health	Limited health care facilities	Fair access; strong private sector	Better primary and secondary healthcare
Living Standards	Poor sanitation and electricity	Moderate; strong in urban LGAs	Good housing, water, and energy access
Economic Structure	Predominantly rural agriculture	Diverse—commerce, industry, agriculture	Mixed—public sector, trade, services
Urbanization	Low	High	Moderate

Drivers of multidimensional poverty

Table 6 presents the respondents' perception of key drivers of multidimensional poverty in the study area. The findings reveal that weak governance was identified as the most prominent driver of multidimensional

poverty, followed by unemployment, insecurity, and food insecurity were perceived as important drivers that play important roles in deepening poverty. Persistent insecurity mechanisms and inadequate service delivery remain critical barriers to rural development in North western Nigeria. The observation aligns with the findings of Usman, & Adeniji, (2023). Interestingly, gender inequality and cultural and religious structures were considered moderate factors compared to other dimensions. This may suggest gradual improvement in gender

inclusion and social change, although traditional norms still shape access to resources, as observed by Isa and Umar

and Ibrahim (2024), who reported that limited education limit farmers' access to innovation, extension services, and market opportunities, thereby perpetuating low productivity and income inequality. Low education as a major driver corresponds with the results of studies using multidimensional poverty indices which identify years of schooling and child school attendance as among the top contributors to deprivation in Nigeria (Akoji & Abaji, 2025). Education limitations reduce access to better jobs, knowledge of health, sanitation, and improved farming practices, reinforcing poverty cycles.

Environmental degradation and limited access to basic amenities such as safe drinking water, sanitation, and electricity were also widely acknowledged as major contributors to multidimensional poverty. These conditions exacerbate vulnerability

by reducing agricultural productivity and quality of life, as similarly noted by Olayemi and Musa (2023) in their study on

poverty reduction strategies. This may suggest that addressing these dimensions is crucial for poverty reduction. Addressing unemployment and insecurity/conflict should be integral to poverty reduction strategies. This includes rural livelihood diversification, conflict resolution, and ensuring safe conditions for farming and market access. Even though gender inequality is perceived by only (2023).

Because weak governance is perceived as such a central driver, efforts to reduce poverty must prioritize institutional strengthening, improving transparency, accountability, and service delivery in rural areas. Enhancing educational access especially at primary and secondary levels is crucial. Scholarships, mobile schooling, adult education, and infrastructure (schools, teachers) are needed. Investments in safe water supply, sanitation, electricity, and healthcare are essential. These not only reduce hardship directly but also support other sectors (education, agriculture).

Addressing unemployment and insecurity/conflict should be integral to poverty reduction strategies. This includes rural livelihood diversification, conflict resolution, and ensuring safe conditions for farming and market access. Even though gender inequality is perceived by only

about half as a major driver, evidence shows it remains a key determinant. Programs should be designed to overcome cultural barriers and enable women's access to education, credit, assets, and decision-making.

In general, the study findings reveal that poverty among farming households in North-western Nigeria is multidimensional,

shaped by the interplay of governance, education, environment, and socio-economic structures. Addressing these drivers requires integrated policy interventions combining institutional reform, improved rural infrastructure, and inclusive human development strategies.

Table 6 Respondents' perception of the drivers of multidimensional poverty among farming households in north western Nigeria

Drivers	Yes	No	Rank
Low educational attainment	223	47	81
Poor health outcomes (limited access to health care)	189	77	274
Limited access to safe drinking water, sanitation and electricity	193		
Food insecurity and malnutrition	182	88	9
Unemployment	190	80	5
Insecurity and conflict	190	80	5
Gender inequality	136	134	10
Weak governance	254	16	1
Environmental degradation	203	67	3
Cultural and religious practices	189	81	7

Coping strategies against multidimensional poverty among farming households in the North-western Nigeria

Table 7 presents the coping strategies adopted by farming households in North-western Nigeria to mitigate the impacts of multidimensional poverty. The study reveal that rural households employ a range of livelihood and consumption-adjustment mechanisms, reflecting both proactive and reactive responses to persistent deprivation. The most widely adopted strategy was diversification of farm enterprises, which ranked first among the coping measures. These finding underscores farmers' recognition of the need to spread production and income risks across multiple crops or

livestock activities. According to Olayemi and Musa (2023), diversification remains a fundamental strategy for improving household resilience in the face of climate variability, market fluctuations, and declining soil fertility in Nigeria's dryland regions. Similarly, Adewuyi et al. (2024) observed that agricultural diversification significantly enhances income stability and food security among smallholder farmers.

The second most common strategy was engagement in off-farm jobs, illustrating the importance of income diversification beyond primary agriculture. Non-farm activities, including petty trading, artisanal work, and transport services, provide crucial buffers against income shocks and seasonal fluctuations. Jimoh, Olagunju, and

Adeniran (2024) reported a similar trend in Northern Nigeria, where better households increasingly depend on formal medical practices, indicating that affluence measures to household resilience and livelihood health options, others are constrained by financial scarcity (Bako and Dango (2023) similarly observed that rural and urban Nigerians. The findings highlight the responses longer than a plan and capital strategies aimed at breaking the intergenerational cycle of poverty. Education and integrated community health groups are delaying children's adaptive and investment strategies. These responses (Mailumo, Aliyu, & Ibrahim, 2024). Begging for survival was the least adopted coping mechanism, possibly due to cultural stigma and personal dignity considerations. Overall, the coping strategies identified (Bello (2023) pattern of adaptive livelihood diversification through skill enhancement, education, and off-farm employment, and Restrictive expenditure measures, such as (i) reactive survival mechanisms such as narrowing spending to basic necessities and borrowing, reduced expenditure, and borrowing from friends, relatives, and neighbors, were also prominent coping mechanisms. These align with findings by Isa and Umar (2023), who emphasized that term consumption adjustments with long-term livelihood adaptation strategies to withstand multidimensional deprivation among low-income households lacking formal credit access. The inadequate access to institutional forces rural dwellers to focus on social networks and communal reciprocity.

Table 7 Coping strategies against multidimensional poverty among farming households in north-western Nigeria

S/NO	Coping strategies	Yes	No	Rank
1.	Engaging in off-farm jobs to raise more income	243	27	2
2.	Borrowed from their friend, relatives and neighbours	184	86	6
3.	Chose to sleep hungry.	75	195	11
4.	Diversification of farm enterprises to counter farm risk and make more income	258	12	1
5.	Forming community self-help groups	127	143	10
6.	Narrow down expenditure to necessities such as food, clothing, education or health	214	56	5
7.	Migration to areas with better economic activities	148	122	9
8.	Enrolling children in free or cheaper schools	235	35	3
9.	Use of orthodox medical practices	173	97	7
10.	Delay in the education of children	168	102	8
11.	Skill acquisition	216	54	4
12.	Begging for survival	11	259	12

Conclusion

The study establishes that farming households in North-western Nigeria experience multidimensional poverty that is both widespread and intense, as evidenced by a high headcount ratio (0.58) and poverty intensity (0.53). This implies that most households face multiple and overlapping deprivations in education, health, and living standards. The findings further highlight weak governance, low education levels, poor access to basic services, and insecurity as major drivers of poverty. While households have developed coping mechanisms such as farm diversification, engagement in off-farm activities, and skill acquisition, these remain largely palliative rather than transformative, reflecting systemic constraints in rural development and institutional support. The large household sizes, low credit access, and moderate education levels reinforce the structural nature of rural poverty, necessitating coordinated policy responses that target

both human and infrastructural deficits.

To address these manifold challenges requires integrated and inclusive development strategies that empower rural households, strengthen governance systems, and build human capital. The evidence underscores that poverty reduction cannot rely solely on income-based interventions but must tackle the root causes that limit access to education, healthcare, and productive resources. A holistic approach involving education, gender inclusion, environmental sustainability, and institutional reform will be essential for breaking the intergenerational cycle of deprivation. The coping patterns observed indicate a high degree of resilience among farming households, which, if supported through the right policy instruments, could serve as the foundation for sustainable rural transformation.

Acknowledgment

The authors are very grateful to the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) for providing the research grants for the study

Recommendations

1. Government at all levels should improve transparency, accountability, and service delivery at the local levels to ensure effective implementation of rural development programs.
2. The state and local governments should introduce functional literacy, adult education, and vocational training to enhance human capital and support innovation adoption.

3. The Government at the state level should promote and encourage non-farm employment opportunities, agro-processing, and small-scale enterprises to enhance household income stability.
4. There should also be investment in water, sanitation, electricity, and healthcare facilities to address critical living standard deprivations.
5. The financial institutions should facilitate access to microcredit and cooperative financing schemes to enable smallholder farmers to expand production and invest in livelihood improvements.

REFERENCES

- Aboaba, K. O., Ogunniyi, A. I., & Olagunju, K. (2019). *Multidimensional poverty among rural households in Nigeria: Evidence from the Alkire-Foster approach*. *Development Studies Research*, 6(1), 112–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2019.1663039>
- Adeyemi, S. A., Musa, H. T., & Ibrahim, U. M. (2024). *Livelihood diversification and poverty reduction strategies among smallholder farmers in Nigeria*. *Journal of Agricultural Policy and Development*, 13(2), 77–91.
- Akoji, S. A., & Abaj, R. (2025). *Economic correlates of multidimensional poverty in Nigeria: Evidence from recent survey data*. *Pan African Journal of Governance and Development*, 6(1), 45–60.
- Alkire, S., & Foster, J. (2011). *Counting and multidimensional poverty measurement*. *Journal of Public Economics*, 95(7–8), 476–487.
- Alkire, S., & Santos, M. E. (2011). *Acute multidimensional poverty: A new index for developing countries*. *Oxford Poverty & Human Development Initiative (OPHI) Working Paper No. 38*. University of Oxford.
- Bako, A. M. (2023). *Rural migration and economic survival strategies in Northwestern Nigeria*. *African Population Studies*, 37(1), 112–126.
- Bello, A., Ahmed, S., & Yusuf, I. (2023). *Gender dynamics and resource access among rural farming households in Northern Nigeria*. *Nigerian Journal of Rural Sociology*, 24(2), 88–103.
- International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD). (2014). *Multidimensional poverty assessment tool: User's guide*. Rome: IFAD.
- Isa, M. A., & Umar, A. A. (2023). *Cultural practices and gendered access agricultural resources in Northwestern Nigeria*. *Journal of Development and Gender Studies*, 11(3), 55–70.
- Jimoh, A. R., Olagunju, F. I., & Adeniran, L. A. (2024a). *Socioeconomic determinants of maize production among smallholder farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria*. *Rural and Agricultural Economics Journal*, 6(1), 23–34.

- Jimoh, O. B., Olagunju, A. K., & Adeniran, T. S. (2024b). *Insecurity, displacement, and agricultural livelihoods in Northern Nigeria*. *Journal of African Development Studies*, 18(1), 101–117.
- Kudaisi, B. V., & Ojeyinka, T. A. (2023). *Governance quality, poverty, and insecurity in Nigeria: Empirical evidence from ARDL and causality analyses*. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 11(1), 35–56.
- Leal Filho, W., Salvia, A. L., Leles, B. C., Paço, A., & Brandli, L. L. (2022). *The role of higher education institutions in supporting sustainable development goals: Insights from Northern Nigeria*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 362, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132325>
- Mailumo, M. A., Aliyu, M., & Ibrahim, Y. (2024a). *Educational attainment and income inequality among rural Nigeria*. *Journal of Agricultural Economics and Policy Studies*, 15(2), 67–82.
- Mailumo, S. S., Aliyu, A., & Ibrahim, A. A. (2024b). *Socio-economic characteristics and constraints of sorghum farmers in Northwest Nigeria*. *Commagri Journal of Agricultural Research*, 9(2), 45–58.
- Mensah N. O., Amrago E. C., Asare J. K., Tutu F. O., Donkor A. (2020): Poultry Farmers Willingness to pay for Agricultural tax: Evidence from the Bono region, Ghana. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development* 17: 290–306.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) & United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2022). *Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) Report 2022*. Abuja: NBS and UNDP.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2021). *2019 Nigeria Poverty and Inequality in Nigeria: Executive Summary*. Abuja: NBS.
- National Population Commission (NPC) [Nigeria] & ICF. (2019). *Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018*. Abuja, Nigeria, and Rockville, Maryland, USA: NPC and ICF.
- Ogunleye, T. S., & Bello, F. A. (2023). *Skill acquisition and livelihood resilience among rural youth in Nigeria*. *Journal of Agricultural and Technical Development*, 9(2), 45–59.
- Olayemi, A. M., & Musa, A. I. (2023). *Environmental degradation and sustainable land management challenges in Nigeria*. *Journal of Environmental and Sustainable Development*, 7(4), 33–49.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2018). *Human Development Indices and Indicators: 2018 Statistical Update*. New York: UNDP.
- Usman, H., & Oladimeji, S. O. (2023). *Institutional quality, governance, and rural poverty in Nigeria: A multidimensional approach*. *Journal of Agricultural Economics and Social Studies*, 65(1), 75–92.
- World Bank. (2023). *Poverty and inequality platform: Nigeria overview*. Washington, D C : World Bank. <https://pip.worldbank.org>
- World Bank. (2023). *Poverty and Inequality Platform: Nigeria Overview*.